

Supplementary material to:

Premature Ovarian Insufficiency in patients with Systemic Lupus Erythematosus on cyclophosphamide: A Systematic review & meta-analysis.

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Supplementary Table 1. Summary of information sources, core search concepts, and records retrieved

Database	Coverage	Core search concepts	Records retrieved
MEDLINE	Inception to October 2024	The electronic search strategy was structured around three core conceptual groups combined with the Boolean operator AND: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cyclophosphamide OR Alkylating drugs OR Chemotherapy agent Primary ovary insufficiency OR Primary ovarian insufficiency OR Primary ovarian failure OR Primary ovary failure OR Premature ovarian insufficiency OR Premature ovary insufficiency OR Premature ovarian failure OR Premature ovary failure OR Premature menopause OR Amenorrhea OR Ovarian damage Systemic lupus erythematosus OR Lupus OR Autoimmune disease The search was performed using combinations of terms from any of these three conceptual groups.	3881
Embase	Inception to October 2024	Same concepts adapted to Emtree terms.	15522
Web of Science	Inception to October 2024	Same concepts adapted to database-specific keywords.	601
Scopus	Inception to October 2024	Same concepts adapted to database-specific keywords.	2611
LILACS	Inception to October 2024	Same concepts adapted to database-specific subject headings and keywords.	23

Searches were structured around three conceptual groups combined with AND: cyclophosphamide/alkylating agents, primary ovarian insufficiency-related outcomes, and systemic lupus erythematosus/autoimmune disease terms. Controlled vocabulary and free-text terms were adapted to each database. No search filters were applied, except in Embase, where a research article filter was used.

Supplementary Table 2. Sensitivity analyses of the primary pooled prevalence estimate according to meta-analytic method

Method	Pooled prevalence (95% CI)	Prediction interval	I ²	Tau ²	Q (p-value)
Freeman-Tukey	15.2 % (6.5-26.4)	0.0-56.3 %	85.1 %	0.0353	73.98 (<0.0001)
Logit-IV	20.0 % (12.7-30.1)	6.9-45.8 %	68.2 %	0.2674	34.59 (0.0003)
GLMM	14.5 % (7.1-27.2)	1.4-66.9 %	54.0 %	1.1391	Wald 23.93 (0.0130)

This table summarizes the pooled prevalence of primary ovarian insufficiency (POI) in cyclophosphamide-exposed women with systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) using three analytical approaches: Freeman-Tukey double arcsine transformation, logit-transformed inverse-variance model, and generalized linear mixed model (GLMM). For each method, the pooled prevalence, 95% confidence interval (CI), prediction interval, and heterogeneity measures are shown. Heterogeneity was assessed using Cochran's Q statistic, I², and tau².

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; GLMM, generalized linear mixed model; IV, inverse variance; POI, premature ovarian insufficiency; SLE, systemic lupus erythematosus.

Supplementary Table 3. Overview of all studies that report POI independent of treatment received

Author (Year)	Design	Country	Age (years)	CYC cumulative dose (gr)	Total patients	Events (POI)	Frecuency (%)	Inclusion criteria	POI Definition
<i>Mok, et al. (1998)</i> ¹	Retrospective cohort	China	Mean not reported	28.3 (mean) No SD report	242	19	7.85	Women < 45 years with other cause of amenorrhea, treated with CYC or other immunosupresive therapy	Sustained amenorrhea with elevated FSH and LH and low estradiol
<i>Medeiros, et al. (2001)</i> ²	Retrospective cohort	Brazil	35.8 (mean) (SD ±5.4)	18.9 (mean) (SD ± 13.1)	71	11	15.49	Women between 16-45 years, without other causes of amenorrhea, and without chronic renal insufficiency	Amenorrhea > 12 months (< 40 years) with FSH > 42 U/L, LH > 11 U/L, estradiol <14 pg/mL
<i>Mok, et al. (2006)</i> ³	Retrospective cohort	China	Mean not reported	100 mg/kg (No detail CD)	243	38	15.64	Lupus nephritis IV, treated with oral or IV CYC and prednisolone	Sustained amenorrhea and postmenopausal FSH and estradiol levels
<i>Silva, et al. (2007)</i> ⁴	Retrospective cohort	Brazil	No POI	No POI	298	0	0	Women ≥ 10 years, post-menarche, Juvenile-onset SLE, without others causes of amenorrhea	Sustained amenorrhea sith FSH ≥ 40 U/L
<i>Appenzeller, et al. (2008)</i> ⁵	Retrospective cohort	Brazil	32 (mean) (range 29-39)	16.8 (mean) (range 14-20)	157	10	6.37	Women < 40 years, Treatment with CYC ≥ 2 years before analysis, without other causes of amenorrhea	Sustained amenorrhea with confirmed hormonal testing (FSH, LH, estradiol)
<i>Mayorga, et al. (2015)</i> ⁶	Cross-sectional	Mexico	32.7 (mean) (SD ±6.2)	33.2 (mean) (SD ± 49.7)	961	52	5.41	Women < 60 years, without other causes of amenorrhea	Amenorrhea ≥ 12 months before age 40, with FSH elevated
<i>Akawatcharangura, et al. (2016)</i> ⁷	Cross-sectional	Thailand	35.8 (mean) (SD ±4.0)	34.9 (mean) (SD ±33.1)	92	11	11.96	≥ 6 months of immunosupresor therapy, without other causes of amenorrhea	Sustained amenorrhea ≥ 6 months, FSH ≥ 40 U/L, estradiol <30 pg/mL
<i>Brunner, et al. (2016)</i> ⁸	Ambispective cohort	USA	No POI	No POI	30	0	0	Childhood-onset SLE, excluded ≥ 19 years, without pregangncy	Secondary amenorrhea ≥ 6 months before age 40, FSH ≥ 40 U/L
<i>Sharma, et al. (2020)</i> ⁹	Prospective cohort	India	No POI	No POI	50	0	0	Women between 18-40 years, severe disease, treated with CYC or Micophenolate, without other causes of amenorrhea	Sustained amenorrhea ≥ 12 months before age 40 and menopausal hormone profile

*All patients have SLE diagnostic by ACR criteria, and other causes of amenorrhea means to surgical, pregnancy or radiotherapy. SD = Standard deviations, IQR = Interquartile range, POI = Premature ovarian insufficiency, CYC = Cyclophosphamide, FSH = Follicle stimulating hormone, LH = Luteinizing hormone, SLE = Systemic lupus erythematosus, USA = United States of America, CD = Cumulative dose.

Supplementary Table 4. Overview of all studies that POI report but the definition not include hormonal profile

Author (Year)	Design	Country	Age (years)	CYC cumulative dose (gr)	Total patients	Events (POI)	Frecuency (%)	Inclusion criteria	POI Definition
Langervits, et al. (1992) ¹⁰	Retrospective case series	Israel	28	11	17	1	5.8	Lupus nephritis: nephrotic syndrome, glucocorticoid or azatioprine not response	Premature menopause in women of 28 years and sustained amenorrhea
Park, et al. (2004)	Retrospective cohort	Korea	35.1 (mean) (SD ±5.0)	9.4 (mean) (SD ± 2.2)	67	10	14.9	Lupus nephritis III or IV, other causes of amenorrhea, uremia	Permanent amenorrhea
Velásquez Méndez, et al. (2006) ¹¹	Cross-sectional	Colombia	35.2 (mean) No SD report	7.36 (mean) No SD report	56	9	16.1	Women < 40 años, without other causes of amenorrhea, without chronic renal failure, and without hormonal therapy	Sustained amenorrhea
Singh, et al. (2007) ¹²	Cross-sectional	India	26.12 (mean) (SD ±8.6)	9.1 (mean) (SD ±2.9)	35	11	31.4	Treatment with CYC (≥ 6 pulses) and 1 year follow-up, without other causes of amenorrhea	Amenorrhea ≥12 months before age 45 years, with menopausal hormones
González, et al. (2008) ¹³	Prospective cohort	USA	28.8 (mean) (SD ±6.1)	Mean not reported	76	25	32.9	Women between 16-40 years, disease duration ≤ 5 years at baseline, without other causes of amenorrhea	Menopause before age 40, regardless of cause
Bozzolo, et al. (2013) ¹⁴	Retrospective cohort	Italy	32.7 (mean) (SD ±4.7)	20.8 (mean) (SD ± 6.4)	29	6	20.7	Lupus nephritis (class III, IV or V), adequate follow-up	Sustained amenorrhea, no strict hormonal criteria detailed in the text
Alarfaj, et al. (2014) ¹⁵	Retrospective cohort	Saudite Arabian	32.4 (mean) (SD ±7.9)	8.3 (mean) (SD ± 2.3)	99	6	6.1	Premenopausal women followed over 26 years, without other causes of amenorrhea	Sustained amenorrhea > 12 months before age 40
Kothari, et al. (2016) ¹⁶	Ambispective cohort	India	≥ 30	≥ 7	27	3	11.1	Women ≥ 13 years, without other connective tissue diseases or gynecological disorder	Irreversible amenorrhea, menopause premature
Ceccareli, et al. (2020) ¹⁷	Cross-sectional	Italy	Mean not reported	Mean not reported	151	8	56	Patients with follow-up in Sapienza Lupus Cohort	Amenorrhea ≥ 12 months before age 40

*All patients have SLE diagnostic by ACR criteria, and other causes of amenorrhea means to surgical, pregnancy or radiotherapy. SD = Standard deviations, IQR = Interquartile range, POI = Premature ovarian insufficiency, CYC = Cyclophosphamide, FSH = Follicle stimulating hormone, LH = Luteinizing hormone, SLE = Systemic lupus erythematosus, USA = United States of America, CD = Cumulative dose.

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Supplementary Figure S1.

Prevalence of POI by period (2008)

Study	Events	Total	Proportion	95%-CI	Weight (common)	Weight (random)
period_2008 = <2008						
McDermott et al., 1996	11	27	0.41	[0.22; 0.61]	2.9%	7.5%
Mok et al., 1998	18	70	0.26	[0.16; 0.38]	7.5%	9.2%
Mok et al., 1999	14	54	0.26	[0.15; 0.40]	5.8%	8.8%
Medeiros et al., 2001	9	26	0.35	[0.17; 0.56]	2.8%	7.4%
Mok et al., 2006	38	188	0.20	[0.15; 0.27]	20.0%	10.2%
Silva et al., 2007	0	59	0.00	[0.00; 0.06]	6.3%	9.0%
Common effect model		424	0.19	[0.15; 0.23]	45.4%	.
Random effects model			0.21	[0.09; 0.36]	.	51.9%
Heterogeneity: $I^2 = 89.9\%$, $\tau^2 = 0.0355$, $p < 0.0001$						
period_2008 = ≥2008						
Appenzeller et al., 2008	10	107	0.09	[0.05; 0.17]	11.4%	9.7%
Mayorga et al., 2015	48	287	0.17	[0.13; 0.22]	30.6%	10.4%
Akawatcharangura et al., 2016	10	64	0.16	[0.08; 0.27]	6.9%	9.1%
Brunner et al., 2016	0	13	0.00	[0.00; 0.25]	1.4%	5.6%
Sharma et al., 2020	0	25	0.00	[0.00; 0.14]	2.7%	7.3%
Orefice et al., 2020	5	15	0.33	[0.12; 0.62]	1.6%	6.0%
Common effect model		511	0.13	[0.10; 0.16]	54.6%	.
Random effects model			0.10	[0.04; 0.18]	.	48.1%
Heterogeneity: $I^2 = 73.9\%$, $\tau^2 = 0.0110$, $p = 0.0018$						
Common effect model		935	0.15	[0.13; 0.18]	100.0%	.
Random effects model			0.15	[0.09; 0.23]	.	100.0%

Heterogeneity: $I^2 = 85.1\%$, $\tau^2 = 0.0201$, $p < 0.0001$
 Test for subgroup differences (common effect): $\chi^2_1 = 5.27$, $df = 1$ ($p = 0.0217$)
 Test for subgroup differences (random effects): $\chi^2_1 = 1.92$, $df = 1$ ($p = 0.1658$)

Supplementary Figure S1. Forest plot of the prevalence of POI in women with SLE treated with CYC, stratified by study period (pre-2008 vs post-2008), The 2008 cut-point corresponds to the year when the Euro-Lupus low-dose CYC regimen was first cited in the EULAR guidance, although it was not yet part of the formal treatment recommendations. A reduction in POI prevalence was observed in post-2008 studies (9.1%, 95% CI 3.5-16.6%), supporting a gradual decline associated with earlier adoption of low-dose protocols.

Supplementary Figure S2.

Supplementary Figure S2. Forest plot of the prevalence of POI in women with SLE treated with CYC, stratified by study period (pre-2019 vs post-2019). The 2019 cut-point corresponds to the publication of the EULAR, which formally endorsed the Euro-Lupus low-dose regimen as a standard induction therapy for lupus nephritis. Only two studies were available in the post-2019 period, yielding wide confidence intervals (10.3%, 95% CI 0-59%) and non-significant subgroup differences ($p = 0.80$), indicating that the decline in POI risk predated the official guideline adoption.

Supplementary Figure S3.

Supplementary Figure S3. Forest plot of premature ovarian insufficiency (POI) prevalence stratified by definition criteria. Studies applying strict hormonal definitions (amenorrhea plus abnormal gonadotrophins/estradiol) yielded a pooled prevalence of 15% (95% CI: 7-26%), while those using broader, clinical definitions (sustained amenorrhea) reported a prevalence of 19% (95% CI: 10-31%).

Supplementary Figure S4.

Supplementary Figure S4. Meta-regression of cumulative cyclophosphamide dose and premature ovarian insufficiency prevalence, showing no significant association.